

Synthesis of trifluoromethylindolocarbazoles, novel cyclic 18-membered and 27-membered *N*-arylmethyl-di- and triindoles and an *N*-arylmethyltetraindolyltrimethane†

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5,11-Dihydro-5,11-diarylmethyl-6-trifluoromethylindolo[3,2-*b*]carbazoles (3b-d) have been synthesised from both *N*-arylmethylindole-3-carbinols (1b-d) and *N,N'*-diarylmethyl-3,3'-diindolylmethanes (2b, c and f) by treatment with trifluoroacetic anhydride. The cyclic *N*-arylmethylindole-di- and trimers (4c-f) and the 3-trifluoroacetylindoles (5a and b) have also been obtained from this reaction. Thermal reaction of 1b-d furnishes 2b, c and f, but 1c also affords the *N*-arylmethyltriindolyldimethane (2d) and the *N*-arylmethyltetraindolyltrimethane (2e). The results are discussed and the plausible reaction mechanism is very briefly presented.

Indolocarbazoles are known to possess important biological activities¹ and 5,11-dialkylindolo[3,2-*b*]carbazole derivatives are used as sedatives, tranquilizers and sunscreen agents². Fluoroorganic compounds have been of great interest to synthetic and medicinal chemists for a long time

due to the unique chemical and biological properties imparted by fluorine and also because of their utilisation as effective drugs, diagnostic agents, agrochemicals and biochemical probes³. So far as we know, fluorine-containing indolocarbazoles are not known in the literature. Therefore, we have recently initiated a programme to develop a method for the synthesis of trifluoromethylindolocarbazoles. In our preliminary endeavour⁴, we studied the reaction of the diindolylmethane (2a) with trifluoroacetic anhydride, since the former can supply two nucleophilic indole moieties and the latter can provide an electrophilic carbonyl carbon and a trifluoromethyl group, which are required for constructing the skeleton of the desired molecule. This reaction gave the indolocarbazole (3a), the 27-membered cyclic *N*-benzylindole trimer (4a) and trifluoroacetylindole (5a). Similar reaction of the indole-3-methanol (1a) furnished (3a, 4a) and the novel 36-membered cyclic *N*-benzylindole tetramer (4b). The macrocyclic compounds 4a and 4b were probably formed by intramolecular cyclisation of the highly reactive intermediate *N*-benzyl-3-indolylmethyl cation at the *para*-position of the *N*-benzyl group.

During the last decade, macrocyclic compounds have become an increasingly important tool in host-guest chemistry and these can be useful not only in pure science but also in various industrial applications⁵. Another motive of our present work was to investigate the scope, limitation and generality of this reaction for the synthesis of macrocyclic indoles by decreasing or increasing the reactivity of the *N*-benzyl residue by introducing a *meta*-bromo or a *meta*-

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- (a), $R^1 = R^2 = H$
- (b), $R^1 = H, R^2 = Br$
- (c), $R^1 = H, R^2 = OMe$
- (d), $R^1 = Ph, R^2 = H$

- (a), $n=2, R^1 = R^2 = R^3 = H$
- (b), $n=3, R^1 = R^2 = R^3 = H$
- (c), $n=2, R^1 = R^2 = H, R^3 = Br$
- (d), $n=2, R^1 = H, R^2 = OMe, R^3 = COCF_3$
- (e), $n=1, R^1 = H, R^2 = OMe, R^3 = COCF_3$
- (f), $n=1, R^1 = Ph, R^2 = R^3 = H$

- (a), $R = H$
- (b), $R = OMe$

methoxy group, and also by introducing a phenyl group on the 3-indolylmethyl carbon. Our results are presented here.

Results and Discussion

The required diindolylmethanes (**2b**, **c** and **f**) were obtained by thermal reactions⁶ of the indole-3-carbinols (**1b**, **c** and **d**), respectively. But **1c** also gave the triindolylmethane (**2d**) and the tetraindolyltrimethane (**2e**).

Reaction of the diindolylmethane (**2b**) with trifluoroacetic anhydride in benzene afforded the 6-trifluoromethylindolo-carbazole (**3b**) as the sole product. As **2b** was prepared from **1b**, we envisaged that this conversion could more conveniently be done *in situ* and our objective might be fulfilled by replacing **2b** by **1b**. Thus, the reaction of **1b** with trifluoroacetic anhydride furnished **3b** and the novel 27-membered cyclic triindole (**4c**). But the reaction of the diindolylmethane (**2c**) with trifluoroacetic anhydride afforded the indolocarbazole (**3c**), the trifluoroacetyl 27-membered cyclic trimer (**4d**) and the 3-trifluoroacetylindole (**5b**), while that of the indole-3-methanol (**1c**) gave the trifluoroacetyl 18-membered cyclic dimer (**4e**) along with **3c**, **4d** and **5b**. Another 18-membered cyclic dimer (**4f**) and the indolocarbazole (**3d**) were obtained together with the trifluoroacetyl diindolylmethane (**2g**) and the trifluoroacetylindole (**5a**) from both the diindolylmethane (**2f**) and the indole-3-carbinol (**1d**)

on treatment with trifluoroacetic anhydride. Macrocyclic indoles of the type **4c-f** having suitable substituents and structural variation may be manipulated to promote molecular recognition and ion-binding⁵.

The protons and carbon of one *N*-CH₂ of **3b-d** resonated in a downfield region in their ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra relative to those of the other *N*-CH₂, probably because the protons and carbon of one *N*-CH₂ bear six-bond and five-bond relationships⁷, respectively with the fluorines of the CF₃ group, whereas there exists no such relationship with those of the other *N*-CH₂. This observation led us to propose structures **3b-d**. This assignment was confirmed by the fact that the 7-H of **3b-d** resonated downfield than 1-H in their ¹H NMR spectra. Similarly, 2-H of **5b** also resonated downfield and showed coupling⁷ with fluorines in its ¹H NMR spectrum. Solutions of **3b-d** in various organic solvents showed blue-violet fluorescence.

The mechanisms of the reactions leading to the products **3b-d** and **4c-f** are similar to those reported in our earlier papers^{4,8} and are very briefly shown in Scheme 1. These have some analogy to literature mechanisms⁹. Formation of **5a** from both **1d** and **2f** and that of **5b** from both **1c** and **2c** provides unambiguous experimental evidence to show that acylation of 3-substituted indoles takes place by initial electrophilic attack at the 3-position followed by migration of the acyl group from the 3-position to the 2-position to afford the observed 2-acyl-3-substituted indoles as Biswas *et al.*⁹ speculated, and contradicts the literature mechanism^{10,11}.

Scheme 1

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. UV spectra (ether or aldehyde-free 95% ethanol) were recorded on a Hitachi U 2000 spectrophotometer, IR spectra (KBr or thin films) on a Perkin-Elmer 782 instrument, NMR spectra (CDCl_3) on a Bruker AM-300L (300 MHz) instrument using TMS as internal standard, and mass spectra on a Jeol SX-102 or Jeol JMS-D-300 machine. Trifluoroacetic anhydride (TFAA) was prepared just before use. Petroleum ether indicates the fraction boiling at 60–80°. Silica gel (60–120 mesh) was used for column chromatography.

All the compounds (**1b-d**, **2b-g**, **3b-d**, **4c-f** and **5b**) gave satisfactory C, H, N analytical data.

Indole-3-carbinols (1b-d) : The compounds were prepared¹² by NaBH_4 reduction of the corresponding carbonyl compounds, which, in turn, were obtained by acylation of indoles. *N*-(*m*-Bromobenzyl)indole-3-carboxaldehyde (81%), m.p. 100–101° (colourless prisms, petroleum ether-benzene), ν_{max} 1650 cm^{-1} (C=O). *N*-(*m*-Methoxybenzyl)indole-3-carboxaldehyde (65.8%), m.p. 113° (colourless prisms, petroleum ether-benzene), ν_{max} 1655 cm^{-1} (C=O). *N*-Benzyl-3-benzoylindole (78.7%), m.p. 156° (white prisms, petroleum ether-benzene), ν_{max} 1620 cm^{-1} (C=O), δ (CDCl_3) 5.32 (2H, s, *N*-CH₂), 7.13–7.87 (13H, m, ArH), 8.53–8.56 (1H, m, H-4), MS (FAB) *m/z* (%) 311 (M^+ , 61). *N*-(*m*-Bromobenzyl)indole-3-methanol (**1b**; 93%), colourless oil, ν_{max} 3640–3200 cm^{-1} (hump, OH). *N*-(*m*-Methoxybenzyl)indole-3-methanol (**1c**; 92.8%), colourless oil, ν_{max} 3390 cm^{-1} (hump, OH). *N*-Benzylindole-3-benzylalcohol (**1d**; 90.5%), m.p. 92–93° (white micro-needles, petroleum ether-benzene), ν_{max} 3450–3080 cm^{-1} (OH), δ (CDCl_3) 5.27 (2H, s, *N*-CH₂), 5.29 (1H, s, 3-CHOH, exchangeable with D₂O), 6.22 (1H, s, 3-CHOH), 6.98–7.68 (14H, m, ArH), MS (FAB) *m/z* (%) 313 (M^+ , 79.1).

Preparation of 2b-f. General procedure : The appropriate indole-3-methanol (0.016 mol) was refluxed with water (25 ml) and methanol (100 ml) for 30 h (in the case of **1d** a few drops of 6 *N* HCl was added to the mixture before heating). The crude product, obtained after evaporation of the solvents in a rotary evaporator, was purified by chromatography over silica gel column. Elution with a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene (9 : 1) furnished **2c**. Further elution with a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene (3 : 1) afforded **2d**. Compounds **2b**, **e** and **f** were eluted with petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1).

N,N'-Di(*m*-bromobenzyl)-3,3'-diindolylmethane (**2b**; 2 g, 43.3%), m.p. 100° (white micro-needles, ether), δ (CDCl_3) 4.18 (2H, s, 15-CH₂), 5.11 (4H, s, 8-CH₂, 8'-CH₂), 6.80

(2H, s, H-2, H-2'), 6.86–7.55 (16H, m, ArH), MS (FAB) *m/z* (%) 584 (M^+ , 100). *N,N'*-Di(*m*-methoxybenzyl)-3,3'-diindolylmethane (**2c**; 1.5 g, 39.3%), creamy semi-solid mass, δ (CDCl_3) 3.72 (6H, s, 11-OCH₃, 11'-OCH₃), 4.30 (2H, s, 15-CH₂), 5.24 (4H, s, 8-CH₂, 8'-CH₂), 6.66 (2H, br s, H-10, H-10'), 6.71 (2H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz, H-13, H-13'), 6.8 (2H, dd, *J* 2.1 and 8.1 Hz, H-12, H-12'), 6.95 (2H, s, H-2, H-2'), 7.08–7.67 (10H, m, ArH), MS (CI) *m/z* 486 (M^+ , 100). *N,N',N''*-Tri(*m*-methoxybenzyl)triindolyl-dimethane (**2d**; 1.7 g, 44.2%), creamy semi-solid mass, δ (CDCl_3) 3.64 (3H, s, 11''-OCH₃), 3.72 (3H, s, 11-OCH₃), 3.77 (3H, s, 11'-OCH₃), 4.33 (2H, s, 15-CH₂), 4.48 (2H, s, 15'-CH₂), 5.04 (2H, s, 8''-CH₂), 5.14 (2H, s, 8-CH₂), 5.30 (2H, s, 8'-CH₂), 6.47–7.77 (26H, m, ArH), MS (CI) *m/z* (%) 735 (M^+ , 100). *N,N',N'',N'''*-Tetra(*m*-methoxybenzyl)tetraindolyltrimethane (**2e**; 0.66 g, 17%), m.p. 165–66° (light orange prisms, ether), ¹H NMR δ (CDCl_3) (assignments given for half of the molecule) 3.60 (3H, s, 11-OCH₃), 3.66 (3H, s, 11'-OCH₃), 4.21 (2H, s, 15-CH₂), 4.53 (2H, s, 15'-CH₂), 4.77 (2H, s, 8-CH₂), 5.12 (2H, s, 8'-CH₂), 6.19 (1H, s, H-2), 6.34 (1H, d, *J* 7.7 Hz, H-12), 6.38 (1H, br s, H-10), 6.45 (1H, d, *J* 7.7 Hz, H-12'), 6.49 (1H, br s, H-10'), 6.74 (2H, td, *J* 2.2 and 8.4 Hz, H-14, H-14'), 6.99 (1H, t, *J* 7.9 Hz, H-13), 7.04–7.63 (8H, m, ArH), ¹³C NMR δ (CDCl_3) 20.12 (C-15'), 20.76 (C-15, C-15''), 46.36 (C-8', C-8''), 49.46 (C-8, C-8'''), 54.77 (11-OCH₃, 11'''-OCH₃), 54.89 (11'-OCH₃, 11''-OCH₃), 109.07, 109.64 (C-7, C-7''', C-7', C-7''), 111.13 (C-12, C-12'''), 111.73, 112.19 (C-3, C-3''', C-3', C-3''), 112.27 (C-12', C-12'', C-10, C-10', C-10'', C-10'''), 117.92, 118.56 (C-4, C-4''', C-4', C-4''), 118.62, 118.98 (C-14, C-6, C-6''', C-14''', C-6', C-6'', C-14', C-14'''), 120.76, 121.59 (C-5, C-5''', C-5', C-5''), 126.88 (C-2, C-2'''), 127.61, 128.41 (C-3a, C-3'''a, C-3''a), 129.41 (C-13, C-13', C-13'', C-13'''), 135.22 (C-7a, C-7'''a), 136.50 (C-2', C-2''), 136.72 (C-7'a, C-7''a), 139.23, 139.94 (C-9, C-9''', C-9', C-9''), 159.64 (C-11, C-11', C-11'', C-11'''), MS (FAB) *m/z* (%) 984 (M^+ , 10.18), 863 [M-(*m*-methoxybenzyl), 6.9], 747 [M-(*m*-methoxybenzyl)indole, 9], 121 (*m*-methoxybenzyl, 91). *N,N'*-Dibenzyl-3,3'-diindolylphenylmethane (**2f**; 2.9 g, 90.6%), m.p. 142° (white spongy mass, benzene-petroleum ether), δ (CDCl_3) 5.25 (4H, s, 8-CH₂, 8'-CH₂), 5.98 (1H, s, H-15), 6.71 (2H, s, H-2, H-2'), 7.0–7.47 (23H, m, ArH); MS (FAB) *m/z* (%) 502 (M^+ , 100).

Reactions of the diindolylmethanes (2b, c and f) with trifluoroacetic anhydride. General procedure :

A solution of freshly prepared trifluoroacetic anhydride (TFAA; 0.04 mol) in sodium-dried benzene (10 ml) was added slowly under a blanket of dry nitrogen to the stirred

solution of appropriate diindolylmethanes (**2b**, **c** and **f**; 0.0016 mol) in dry benzene (50 ml) at 0–5° and the stirring was continued at 0–5° for 1 h and at the room temperature for 4 h. The crude product, obtained after removal of the solvent, etc. on a rotary evaporator, was purified by column chromatography using silica gel. Elution of the column with a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene (9 : 1) furnished **2g**, **3b**, **3d** and **5a**, **b**. Further elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (3 : 1) afforded **2g**, **3c** and **4f**. Compound **4d** was eluted with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 1). Their physical and spectral characteristics are given below.

5,11-Dihydro-5-(3'-bromo)benzyl-11-(3''-bromo)benzyl-6-trifluoromethylindolo[3,2-b]carbazole (3b); 0.28 g, 29%), m.p. 199–200° (yellow needles, benzene-petroleum ether), λ_{\max} (ether) (log ϵ) 238 (4.43), 262.5 (4.52), 335 (4.42), 348 (4.6), 382 (4.58), 389 (3.74), 410 nm (3.86), $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (CDCl₃) 5.40 (2H, s, 11-CH₂), 5.54 (2H, s, 5-CH₂), 6.92–7.46 (14H, m, ArH), 8–8.02 (1H, m, H-1), 8.02 (1H, s, H-12), 8.33–8.35 (1H, m, H-7), $^{13}\text{C NMR } \delta$ (CDCl₃) 46.01 (11-CH₂), 52.7 (5-CH₂), 102.96 (C-12), 108.62 (C-4), 111.07 (C-10), 119.56 (C-2), 119.82 (C-1), 120.48 (C-8), 121.26 (C-12a), 122.72 (C-6a), 123.06 (C-6b), 123.26 (C-3', C-3''), 124.53 (C-7), 124.66 (C-3, C-9), 126.55 (C-12b), 126.56 (C-6''), 127.32 (C-6'), 129 (C-4''), 129.25 (C-4'), 130.09 (C-5', C-5''), 130.44 (C-2''), 130.82 (C-2'), 136.46 (C-6), 139.13 (C-10a, C-1''), 140.41 (C-4a, C-1'), 141.83 (C-11a), 145.31 (C-5a), MS (EI) m/z (%) 664 (19.2), 663 (55.1), 662 (M⁺, 38.4), 661 (100), 493 (M-*m*-bromobenzyl, 79), 324 (M-2×*m*-bromobenzyl, 6), 169 (*m*-bromobenzyl, 71).

Reaction of **1b** with TFAA under similar reaction conditions furnished **3b** (10%) along with the cyclic trimer **4c**.

27-Membered cyclic N-(m-bromobenzyl)indole trimer (4c); 2%), m.p. 212–13° (yellow needles, benzene-petroleum ether), $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (CDCl₃) (assignments are given for one indole unit only) 3.86 (2H, s, 15-CH₂), 5.19 (2H, s, 8-CH₂), 6.69–7.40 (8H, m, ArH), MS (FAB) m/z (%) 895 (100), 894 (M⁺, 84.7), 893 (90.21), 892 (46.12), 891 (30.71), 595 (35.02), 298 (50.61).

N-(m-Methoxybenzyl)-3-trifluoroacetylindole (5b); 20%), m.p. 70° (colourless needles, benzene-petroleum ether), ν_{\max} 1665 cm⁻¹ (COCF₃), $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (CDCl₃) 3.76 (3H, s, 11-OCH₃), 5.36 (2H, s, 8-CH₂), 6.71 (1H, br s, H-10), 6.76 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, H-12), 6.87 (1H, dd, *J* 2.2 and 8.2 Hz, H-14), 7.25–7.40 (4H, m, ArH), 7.98–7.99 (1H, m, H-2), 8.41–8.45 (1H, m, H-4), $^{13}\text{C NMR } \delta$ (CDCl₃) 50.92 (C-8), 54.93 (OCH₃), 109.67 (C-3), 110.65 (C-7), 112.84 (C-12), 113.21 (C-10), 118.94 (C-14), 122.28 (C-4), 123.76 (C-6), 124.49 (C-5), 126.88 (C-3a), 130.04 (C-

13), 136.18 (C-9), 136.66 (C-7a), 137.65 (C-2), 159.96 (C-11), 174.41 and 174.87 (COCF₃), MS (FAB) m/z (%) 334 (100), 333 (M⁺, 80.6), 264 (M-CF₃, 23), 226 (M-methoxyphenyl, 8.5), 121 (*m*-methoxybenzyl, 77.7), 91 (12.33), 77 (5.96).

5,11-Dihydro-5-(3'-methoxy)benzyl-11-(3''-methoxy)benzyl-6-trifluoromethylindolo[3,2-b]carbazole (3c); 24%), m.p. 210° (yellow prisms, benzene-petroleum ether) λ_{\max} (ether) (log ϵ) 221 (4.7), 262 (4.5), 282 (4.6), 348 (4.6), 391 (3.7), 412 nm (4.2), $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (CDCl₃) 3.72 (3H, s, 3''-OCH₃), 3.74 (3H, s, 3'-OCH₃), 5.47 (2H, s, 11-CH₂), 5.58 (2H, s, 5-CH₂), 6.73–7.52 (14H, m, ArH), 8.04 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, H-1), 8.11 (1H, s, H-12), 8.42–8.44 (1H, m, H-7), $^{13}\text{C NMR } \delta$ (CDCl₃) 46.69 (11-CH₂), 53.16 (5-CH₂), 55.09 (3''-OCH₃, 3'-OCH₃), 103.14 (C-12), 108.77 (C-4), 111.45 (C-10), 119.96 (C-4''), 112.41 (C-4', C-2''), 112.73 (C-2'), 118.44 (C-2), 118.53 (C-1), 119.28 (C-8), 119.69 (C-6''), 120.21 (C-6'), 120.74 (C-12a), 121.36 (C-6a), 123.43 (C-6b), 124.54 (C-7), 126.47 (C-12b), 126.65 (C-9), 127.09 (C-3), 129.43 (C-5''), 129.94 (C-5'), 136.78 (C-6), 138.55 (C-10a, C-1''), 139.70 (C-4a, C-1'), 142.18 (C-11a), 145.65 (C-5a), 160 (C-3''), 160.27 (C-3'), MS (FAB) m/z (%) 564 (M⁺, 90.53), 334 (M-*m*-methoxytoluene-anisole, 100), 121 (*m*-methoxybenzyl, 78.92).

Trifluoroacetyl 27-membered cyclic N-(m-methoxybenzyl)indole trimer (4d); 4%), m.p. 160°d (white spongy mass, benzene-petroleum ether), ν_{\max} 1685 cm⁻¹ (COCF₃), $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (CDCl₃) 3.10 (2H, s, 15''-CH₂), 3.43 (3H, s, 11''-OCH₃), 3.68 (3H, s, 11'-OCH₃), 3.82 (3H, s, 11-OCH₃), 4.38 (2H, s, 15-CH₂), 4.90 (2H, s, 15'-CH₂), 5.23 (2H, s, 8''-CH₂), 5.26 (2H, s, 8'-CH₂), 5.29 (2H, s, 8-CH₂), 6.10 (1H, br s, H-10'), 6.22 (1H, d, *J* 7.7 Hz, H-14'), 6.38 (1H, br s, H-10''), 6.45 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz, H-13''), 6.62 (1H, dd, *J* 2.6 and 6 Hz, H-13), 6.74 (1H, td, *J* 2 and 7.9 Hz, H-14''), 6.91–7.49 (16H, m, ArH), 8.14 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, H-7), MS (FAB) m/z (%) 843 (M⁺, 32), 497 [M-3-(2'-methoxy-5'-trifluoroacetyl)benzyl-1-indolylmethyl, 100], 121 (68.2).

Reaction of the indole-3-methanol **1c** with TFAA under similar reaction conditions afforded the same three products **3c** (12%), **4d** (6%) and **5b** (3%) along with the novel cyclic dimer (**4e**).

Trifluoroacetyl 18-membered cyclic dimer (4e); 2%), m.p. 222° (cream coloured needles, benzene-petroleum ether), ν_{\max} 1670 cm⁻¹ (COCF₃), $^1\text{H NMR } \delta$ (CDCl₃) 3.27 (2H, s, 15-CH₂), 3.66 (3H, s, 11'-OCH₃), 3.82 (3H, s, 11-OCH₃), 5.06 (2H, s, 15'-CH₂), 5.22 (2H, s, 8'-CH₂), 5.45 (2H, s, 8-CH₂), 6.31 (1H, br s, H-10'), 6.41 (1H, d, *J* 7.55

Hz, H-13'), 6.63–7.29 (11H, m, ArH), 7.68–7.71 (1H, m, H-2), 8.05–8.08 (1H, d, *J* 8.04 Hz, H-7), ¹³C NMR δ (CDCl₃) 22.85 (C-15), 28.61 (C-15'), 46.10 (C-8'), 48.09 (C-8), 54.97 (11'-OCH₃), 55.27 (11-OCH₃), 107.31 (C-3, C-3'), 109.13 (C-7'), 111.08 (C-7), 111.55 (C-10'), 112.26 (C-10), 112.66 (C-14'), 117.12 (C-4'), 117.84 (C-4), 118.16 (C-6'), 119.67 (C-6), 121.06 (C-5'), 122.31 (C-5), 123.12 (C-2'), 123.43 (C-2), 125.60 (C-12'), 127.16 (C-3'a), 128.37 (C-3a), 129.70 (C-13'), 131.99 (C-12), 132.28 (C-13), 135.43 (C-9'), 136.3 (C-7'a), 136.60 (C-7a), 139.12 (C-9), 150.42 (C-14), 158.69 (C-11'), 160.23 (C-11), 177.41 (COCF₃), MS (FAB) *m/z* (%) 594 (M⁺, 100), 121 (*m*-methoxybenzyl, 50.4).

5,11-Dihydro-5,11-dibenzyl-12-phenyl-6-trifluoroethylindolo[3,2-b]carbazole (3d; 2%), m.p. 224° (yellow prisms, benzene-petroleum ether); λ_{max} (ether) (log ε) 221 (4.88), 225.5 (4.88), 257.5 (4.56), 285 (4.73), 333 (4.47), 346.5 (4.64), 390.5 (3.89), 411.5 nm (4.62), ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃) 5.07 (2H, s, 11-CH₂), 5.47 (2H, s, 5-CH₂), 6.21–7.43 (22H, m, ArH), 8.36–8.38 (1H, m, H-7), ¹³C NMR δ (CDCl₃) 47.55 (11-CH₂), 53.67 (5-CH₂), 109.11 (C-4), 110.91 (C-10), 119.29 (C-2), 119.79 (C-1), 120.69 (C-6a, C-12a), 122.13 (C-8), 123.50 (C-6b, C-12b), 124.42 (C-7), 125.19 (C-3'', C-5''), 125.90 (C-3', C-5'), 126.39 (C-3), 126.62 (C-4''), 126.76 (C-4', C-9), 128.09 (C-4'''), 128.39 (C-2'', C-6'', C-2''', C-6'''), 128.70 (C-2', C-6'), 129.63 (C-3''', C-5'''), 133.60 (C-6), 136.55 (C-10a, C-1''), 137.46 (C-4a, C-1'), 137.87 (C-12), 142.86 (C-11a), 145.48 (C-5a, C-1'''), MS (FAB) *m/z* (%) 580 (M⁺, 100), 512 (M-CF₃+H, 5.6), 503 (M-Ph, 7.2), 489 (M-PhCH₂, 22.5), 330 (M-2×PhCH₂-CF₃+H, 8), 91 (43.4).

18-Membered cyclic dimer (4f; 2%), m.p. 318° (white micro-needles, benzene-petroleum ether), ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃) 4.90 (2H, d, *J* 17.2 Hz, H_A-8, H_A-8'), 5.22 (2H, d, *J* 17.2 Hz, H_B-8, H_B-8'), 5.50 (2H, s, H-15, H-15'), 6.67–7.32 (28H, m, ArH), ¹³C NMR δ (CDCl₃) 40.04 (C-15, C-15'), 46.62 (C-8, C-8'), 109.28 (C-7, C-7'), 112.68 (C-3, C-3'), 119.11 (C-4, C-4'), 119.20 (C-6, C-6'), 121.40 (C-5, C-5'), 125.68 (C-2, C-2'), 125.77 (C-11, C-11', C-13, C-13'), 126.60 (C-3a, C-3'a), 126.91 (C-4'', C-4'''), 128.49 (C-2'', C-2''', C-6'', C-6''', C-10, C-10', C-14, C-14'), 128.72 (C-3'', C-3''', C-5'', C-5'''), 136.01 (C-7a, C-7'a), 137.84 (C-12, C-12'), 138.14 (C-9, C-9'), 143.39 (C-1'', C-1'''), MS (FAB) *m/z* (%) 590 (M⁺, 100), 513 (M-Ph, 28.5), 331 (M-Ph-2×PhCH₂, 27.7).

N,N'-Dibenzylindolyl-3,3'-(5-trifluoroacetyl)indolyl-phenylmethane (2g; 4%), m.p. 213° (colourless micro-needles, benzene-petroleum ether), ν_{max} 1675 cm⁻¹

(COCF₃), λ_{max} (ether) nm (log ε) 227 (4.77), 254.5 (4.41), 299 (4.22), 314.5 (4.17), 381 (3.11), ¹H NMR δ (CDCl₃) 5.17 (2H, s, 8-CH₂), 5.26 (2H, s, 8'-CH₂), 5.80 (1H, s, H-15), 6.52 (1H, s, H-2''), 6.97 (1H, s, H-2'), 6.86–7.30 (20H, m, ArH), 7.84–7.85 (1H, m, H-6'), 8.32 (1H, br s, H-4'), ¹³C NMR δ (CDCl₃) 48.85 (C-15), 49.80 (C-8'), 51.21 (C-8), 109.63 (C-7'), 110.42 (C-7), 118.94 (C-4'), 119.02 (C-3, C-3'), 119.88 (C-4, C-6'), 121.71 (C-6), 122.54 (C-5'), 125.91 (C-2, C-2'), 126.09 (C-4''), 126.21 (C-11', C-13'), 126.95 (C-11, C-13), 127.25 (C-12'), 127.50 (C-3a, C-3'a), 128.19 (C-2'', C-6''), 128.38 (C-12), 128.58 (C-10', C-14'), 128.76 (C-10, C-14), 129.02 (C-3'', C-5''), 134.62 (C-9'), 135.52 (C-9), 136.92 (C-7'a), 137.62 (C-7a), 140.24 (C-5), 144.02 (C-1''), 174.36 (COCF₃), MS (FAB) *m/z* (%) 599 (57.88), 598 (M⁺, 100), 522 (M-Ph⁺H, 6.65), 521 (M-Ph, 15.75), 507 (M-PhCH₂, 5.68), 392 (M-N-benzyl-3-indolyl, 26.6), 91 (PhCH₂, 21.7), 77 (C₆H₅, 5.1).

N-Benzyl-3-trifluoroacetylindole (5a; 50%), m.p. 104° (lit.⁴ 104°) (colourless fine needles, benzene-petroleum ether).

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